

Contrasting solvent effects on the kinetics of oxidation of methionine by quinolinium fluorochromate

D. S. Bhuvaneshwari, B. John, M. Pandeewaran and K. P. Elango*

Department of Chemistry, Gandhigram Rural Institute (Deemed University), Gandhigram-624 302, India

E-mail : drkpelango@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-451-2454466

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The oxidation of methionine by quinolinium fluorochromate (QFC) has been studied, in the presence of chloroacetic acid, in water-DMSO and water-acetic acid mixtures of varying mole fractions. The reaction is first order each with respect to methionine, QFC and acid. The reaction rates have been determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters have been computed. The reaction rate increases with increase in mole fraction of acetic acid in the mixture, where the specific solvent-solvent-solute interactions were found to dominant (56%), while in water-DMSO mixtures the rate decreases with increasing mole fraction of the organic co-solvent, where the transition state was stabilized only to a lesser extent by solvation. A solvation model and a suitable mechanism for the reaction are postulated.

Our studies¹ of the kinetics of oxidation of organic compounds in non-aqueous and aquo-organic solvent mixtures have revealed the important role of non-specific and specific solvent effects on the reactivity. It has been shown that the reactivity is influenced by the preferential solvation of the reactants and/or transition state through non-specific and specific solvent-solvent-solute interactions. Furthermore, it has been established that the technique of correlation analysis may well be used to separate and quantify such solvent-solvent-solute interactions on reactivity.

Extensive studies on the mechanism of oxidation of methionine (Met) by several oxidants have been reported. This sulphur containing essential amino acid is reported to behave differently, in comparison to other amino acids, towards many oxidants². This may well be due to the presence of an electron-rich sulphur centre, which is easily oxidisable. Quinolinium fluorochromate (QFC) is reported to be a mild, stable and selective oxidant³. A perusal of literature showed that there seems to be a very few reports using QFC. In this article, we report the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of methionine by QFC in water-DMSO and water-acetic acid mixtures of varying mole fractions, with a view to understand the utility of solvent variation studies in understanding the mechanism of this biologically important amino acid because it may reveal the mechanism of amino acid metabolism. Furthermore, solvent mixtures are very useful for studying solvent effects upon reactions since the properties of various mixed solvents can be adjusted continuously by changing the composition of the mixture.

Results and discussion

The reactions are first order with respect to QFC. Further, the values of k_{obs} are independent of the initial concentration of QFC (Table 1). The reaction rate increases linearly with increase in the concentration of Met. The order of the reaction with respect to Met is also one. The re-

Table 1. Pseudo-first order rate constants for the oxidation of methionine by QFC in water at $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$

10^2 [Met] (M)	10^3 [QFC] (M)	10 [Acid] (M)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1})
1.0	1.00	3.0	2.20
1.5	1.00	3.0	2.85
2.0	1.00	3.0	4.28
2.5	1.00	3.0	5.29
3.0	1.00	3.0	6.12
2.0	1.00	3.0	2.85 ^a
2.0	1.00	3.0	4.28
2.0	1.25	3.0	4.31
2.0	1.50	3.0	4.28
2.0	1.75	3.0	4.29
2.0	2.00	3.0	4.12
2.0	1.00	1.0	1.57
2.0	1.00	2.0	2.94
2.0	1.00	3.0	4.28
2.0	1.00	4.0	6.24
2.0	1.00	5.0	7.23

^aContained $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M Mn}^{\text{II}}$.

action is catalysed by hydrogen ions and the order with respect to $[H^+]$ is one. Therefore, the rate law can be represented as :

$$-d[QFC]/dt = k [Met] [QFC] [H^+]$$

The oxidation of Met in an atmosphere of nitrogen failed to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the rate of oxidation decreases with the addition of Mn^{II} indicating the involvement of a two electron reduction of Cr^{VI} to Cr^{IV} . Therefore, a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals is unlikely. The rate of oxidation of Met was determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated as : $\Delta H^\ddagger = 19.8 \pm 0.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -211 \pm 3 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $\Delta G^\ddagger = 84.7 \pm 0.6 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. These activation parameters are comparable with those for the oxidation of Met by other halochromates².

The influence of solvent on the rate of the reaction was studied in water-organic solvent mixtures at different mole fractions of organic co-solvent viz. acetic acid (protic, hydrogen bond donor) and DMSO (aprotic, non-hydrogen bond donor). The results in Table 2 indicate that the rate constants (k_2) are remarkably sensitive to the nature and the composition of the mixed solvent. The rate constants increase with increasing mole fraction of acetic acid while decrease with increasing mole fraction of DMSO in the mixture.

Table 2. Effect of organic co-solvent on the rate constant ($10^4 k_2, \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) for the oxidation of methionine by QFC at $25 \pm 1^\circ \text{C}$ $[Met] = 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$; $[QFC] = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ and $[H^+] = 3 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}$

Mole-fraction of organic co-solvent	0	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
Water-AcOH mixtures	214	333	346	575	801	1150	1259	1469
Water-DMSO mixtures	214	49	28	22	12	10.3	10.4	10.0

The influence of relative permittivity on the rate can be described by the equation of Laidler and Eyring⁴.

$$d \ln k/d(1/\epsilon_r) = e^2 Z^2 (1/r - 1/r^*)/2kT$$

where k is the rate constant, Z the net charge, r the effective radius and r^* is the radius of the activated species. A non-linear plot (in water-acetic acid mixtures $r = 0.933$, $sd = 0.13$, $\psi = 0.42$ and in water-DMSO mixtures $r = 0.962$, $sd = 0.12$, $\psi = 0.32$) of $\log k_2$ versus the reciprocal of the relative permittivity, ϵ_r , is found in both the aquo-organic solvent mixtures investigated, which implies a differential solvation between the initial state and the transition state.

The solvent effect was also analysed using the Grunwald-Winstein equation⁵ :

$$\log k = \log k_o + mY$$

where Y is an empirical parameter (solvent ionizing power) characteristic of the given solvent and m is a substrate parameter measuring the substrate sensitivity to changes in the ionizing power of the medium. A plot of $\log k_2$ versus Y in water-acetic acid mixtures (for the other mixture Y values are not available) is also non-linear ($r = 0.968$, $sd = 0.09$, $\psi = 0.29$). The statistical results indicate that the correlation between $\log k_2$ and the macroscopic solvent parameters such as relative permittivity and ionizing power is poor. That is no single macroscopic solvent parameter can explain the solvent effect on reactivity completely.

From idealized theories, the solvent relative permittivity is often predicted to serve as a quantitative measure of solvent polarity. However, this approach is often inadequate since these theories regard solvents as a non-structured continuum, not composed of individual solvent molecules with their own solvent-solvent interactions and they do not take into account specific solute-solvent interactions, such as hydrogen bonding and electron pair donor-electron pair acceptor interactions, which often play a dominating role in solute-solvent interactions. No single macroscopic physical parameter could possibly account for the multitude of solute-solvent interactions on the molecular microscopic level⁶. Thus, bulk solvent properties like the relative permittivity and ionizing power will poorly describe the microenvironment around the reacting species, which governs the stability of the transition state and hence the rate of the reaction. Hence, there have been a variety of attempts to quantify different aspects of solvent polarity and then use the resultant parameters to interpret solvent effects on reactivity through multiple regression. Various treatments for the above solvent-solvent-solute interactions based on linear solvation energy relationships (LSER) have been developed⁶.

The effect of solvent on reactivity may be understood from the standpoint of specific solvation effect and non-specific solvation effect. This kind of dual dependency of reactivity on solvent composition is illustrated by Kamlet-Taft's solvatochromic comparison method⁷. This method may be used to unravel, quantify, correlate and rationalize multiple interacting solvent effects on reactivity. Thus the rate data were correlated with the solvatochromic parameters in the form of the following Linear Solvation Energy Relationship (LSER).

$$\log k = A_o + s \pi^* + a \alpha + b \beta$$

where π^* is an index of solvent dipolarity/polarizability, which measures the ability of the solvent to stabilize a charge or a dipole by virtue of its dielectric effect, α is the solvent HBD (hydrogen bond donor) acidity, β is the solvent HBA (hydrogen bond acceptor) basicity of the solvent in a solute to solvent hydrogen bond and A_0 is the regression value of the solute property in the reference solvent cyclohexane. The regression coefficients s , a and b measure the relative susceptibilities of the solvent dependent solute property $\log k_2$ to the indicated solvent parameter. The rate of oxidation in both the solvent mixtures studied show good correlations with solvent via the above LSER. The correlation results obtained are given under.

In water-acetic acid mixtures :

$$\log k_2 = -2.365 - 2.466 \pi^* + 0.349 \alpha + 2.742 \beta$$

($N = 8$, $R^2 = 0.979$, $sd = 0.12$, $\psi = 0.18$, $P_\alpha = 7\%$, $P_\beta = 49\%$, $P_{\pi^*} = 44\%$)

In water-DMSO mixtures :

$$\log k_2 = -0.197 - 1.288 \pi^* + 0.893 \alpha - 2.393 \beta$$

($N = 8$, $R^2 = 0.987$, $sd = 0.07$, $\psi = 0.14$, $P_\alpha = 20\%$, $P_\beta = 52\%$, $P_{\pi^*} = 28\%$)

Such a good correlation, with an explained variance of ca. 99% in both the aquo-organic solvent mixtures, indicates the existence of non-specific and specific solvent-solute interactions. From the values of the regression coefficients the contribution of each parameter (P_x), on a percentage basis, to reactivity were calculated¹.

The observation of this systematic multiple regression analysis leads us to the following preliminary conclusions. (i) In water-acetic acid mixtures, the rate of the reaction is strongly influenced by specific solute-solvent interactions as indicated by the percentage contributions of α and β parameters. (ii) The positive sign of the coefficients of α and β terms suggest that the specific interactions between the transition state and the solvent, through HBD and HBA properties, is more than that between the reactants and the solvent. (iii) In water-acetic acid mixture the contribution of the solvent HBA basicity β to the total solvent effect is predominant. The positive sign of the coefficient of this term suggests that the solvent mixture solvates the transition state more than reactants. Since acetic acid in an amphiprotic solvent, increase in its mole fraction in the mixture may stabilize the transition state through better solvation through HBD and HBA interactions and consequently increase the rate of the oxidation. (iv) The solvent dipolarity/polarizability π^* also plays an appreciable role. The negative sign of the coefficient of this term suggests that the reactants are extensively solvated by the solvents

than the transition state. (v) In water-DMSO mixtures also, the rate of the reaction is strongly influenced by specific solute-solvent interactions as indicated by the percentage contributions of α and β parameters. (vi) The contribution of the solvent hydrogen bond acceptor property β to the total solvent effect is predominant. The negative sign of the coefficient of this term indicates that the solvation of the reactants by the solvent mixture is extensive. Since DMSO is a typical HBA solvent, increase in its mole fraction in the mixture decreases the rate of the reaction by stabilizing the reactants. (vii) The rate of the reaction is also influenced by π^* which is a measure of the solvent to stabilize a charge or a dipole by virtue of its dielectric effect. The negative sign of the coefficients of this term suggest that the non-specific interaction between the reactants and the solvent is more than that between the transition state and the solvent.

Considering these points the solvation model for the oxidation of methionine by QFC in water-acetic acid and water-DMSO mixtures can be represented as :

In water-DMSO mixtures :

Further, there exists a dynamic exchange of solvent molecules between the solvation shell of the transition state and the bulk⁸. As the organic co-solvent concentration increases in the mixture, more and more number of organic solvent molecules are introduced into the solvation shell. Plot of $\log k_2$ versus mole fraction of the co-solvents, x_2 , show separate lines for water-acetic acid and water-DMSO mixture. The difference in slope values between the two lines is a measure of solvent participation in the solvation process.

Mechanism : Under the experimental conditions employed in the present study methionine is oxidized to the corresponding sulphoxide stage only. Based on the above kinetic observations i.e. first order dependence each on

[Met], [QFC] and [acid] the following mechanism is proposed for the reaction. The linear increase in rate with acidity suggests the involvement of protonated QFC in the rate-determining step. In the first step QFC gets protonated. The protonated QFC attacks the substrate, in a slow step, to form a complex, which subsequently decomposes to give the products in a fast step. The proposed scheme envisages an oxygen atom transfer from the oxidant and that is in agreement with earlier observations involving the oxidation of sulphur containing compounds with QFC. The electrophilic attack on the sulphide-sulphur can be viewed as an S_N2 reaction. An S_N2 like transition state is supported by the observed solvent effect.

The oxidation of methionine by QFC is first order each with respect to [Met], [QFC] and [acid]. Under the experimental conditions methionine is oxidized to the corresponding sulphoxide stage only. The entropy of activation is negative suggesting the formation of a complex in the slow step.

The reaction is highly influenced by the amount and nature of the organic co-solvent added to the mixture. Linear and multiple regression analysis may be used to separate and quantify the specific and non-specific solvational effects on the oxidation of methionine by QFC. Using the above method the significance of those solvent-solvent-solute interactions on the reactivity has been established. From the regression coefficients information on the solvent-reactant and the solvent-transition state interactions is obtained and the solvation models are proposed.

Experimental

Methionine (Merck) was used as supplied. QFC was prepared by the reported method³ and its purity was checked by iodometric assay. Monochloroacetic acid was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Solvents were purified by the standard methods.

Kinetic measurements : The reaction was studied under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping an excess of the substrate over the oxidant. The solvent was pure water unless mentioned otherwise. The reactions were studied at constant temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$) in the presence of chloroacetic acid (0.3 M) and were followed up to 80% completion by

monitoring the decrease in [QFC] iodometrically. Pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were evaluated from the linear plots of ($r^2 > 0.97$) $\log [\text{QFC}]$ against time. Triplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants are reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The specific rate constant, k_2 , were computed from the relation; $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{Met}]$.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by performing the experiment under the conditions of $[\text{QFC}] > [\text{Met}]$. The disappearance of QFC was monitored until constant titre values were obtained.

The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. The oxidation of Met resulted in the formation of the corresponding sulphoxide. The sulphoxide was determined by the reported method⁹. The yield of the sulphoxide was $86 \pm 4\%$.

Data analysis : Correlation analyses were carried out using Microcal Origin (version 3.5) computer software. The goodness of the fit was discussed using correlation coefficient, r , in the case of simple regression and R in the case of multiple regression analysis, standard deviation, sd , and Exner's statistical parameter, ψ .

References

1. G. Fatima Jeyanthi and K. P. Elango, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2003, **35**, 154; S. Saravanna kanna and K. P. Elango, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2002, **34**, 585; J. R. C. Ramya Vijayakumari and K. P. Elango, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 834; V. Ramesh, M. Sumathy, K. Karunakaran and K. P. Elango, *Oxidn. Commun.*, 2001, **24**, 241; K. P. Elango, *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **66**, 359.
2. A. Goyal and S. Kothari, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2003, **42**, 2129; V. Sharma, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **36**, 418; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 607.
3. V. Murugesan and A. Pandurangan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1992, **31**, 377.
4. E. S. Amis and J. F. Hinton, "Solvent Effect of Chemical Phenomena", Vol. 1, Academic Press, New York, 1973.
5. A. H. Fainberg and S. Winstein, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 2770.
6. C. Reichardt, "Solvents and Solvent Effects in Organic Chemistry", VCR. Weinheim, 1988.
7. M. J. Kamlet, J. M. Abboud, M. H. Abraham and R. W. Taft, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, **48**, 2877.
8. Y. Marcus, "Ion Solvation". Wiley, New York, 1985.
9. S. Goel, S. Kothari and K. K. Banerji, *J. Chem. Res. (M)*, 1996, 1318.